

The Discovery of Oxygen

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In ordinary text-books it is customary to dispose of the rival claims of Lavoisier and Priestley cavalierly and in a summary fashion. The former is often held up to public opprobrium as a plagiarist, as one who had heard of the discovery of oxygen from the lips of Priestley himself but forgot to acknowledge his obligations and thus indirectly and by implication, at any rate, claimed it as his own.² As this vexed question has been puzzling the brains of many an historian of chemistry for the last century and a half, it is much to be desired that a final and definitive solution, if possible, should be arrived at. We, as Indians—as a third party—can afford to judge the question impartially, for, we do not hold a brief either for the English or for the French and thus can adjudicate between the rival claims.

¹ Presidential address delivered at the Second Annual General meeting of the Indian Chemical Society held at Bombay on the 2nd January, 1926.

² "Many of the charges which have been brought against Lavoisier's good faith unfortunately turn out upon investigation to be well-founded, so that whilst we must greatly admire the clear sight of the philosopher, we cannot feel the same degree of respect for the moral character of the man"—Rosecoe and Schorlemmer.

Liebig goes a step further and scarcely even mentions the name of Lavoisier and cites only Black, Cavendish and Priestley among the creators of chemistry, who flourished towards the end of the eighteenth century. Volhard still further improves upon Liebig's verdict. According to him Lavoisier has only appropriated to himself the discoveries of others and has never noticed a new property of a single body. Volhard was evidently smarting under the sting of the well-known passage of Wurtz: "La chimie est une science française." Moreover, he wrote the above in 1870, when the Franco-Prussian war had broken out. It is thus evident that even in a scientific controversy the bias of patriotism comes into play and prevents the formation of a correct estimate of a man's greatness and worth. Kopp also does him but bare justice (*Gen. Chem.*, Vol. 1, p. 306).

Priestley was a born theologian, a controversialist and a linguist to boot. He pursued chemistry simply as a recreation during his leisure hours and as a mere hobby. He had thus to approach the subject without any previous systematic training. As he himself candidly admits: "Had I been anything of a practical chymist, I could not have entertained any such suspicion about mercurius calcinatus on which I had made my experiments." On another occasion in describing the *air from nitre* he says: "This series of facts, relating to air extracted, seem very extraordinary, and important, *and in able hands* may lead to considerable discoveries." Moreover, he had to struggle with poverty, and much of his time was taken up in earning his livelihood as a pastor or tutor. Lavoisier, on the other hand, was born in an opulent family and his father spared no pains to give his son the benefit of a liberal education. He studied mathematics and astronomy, mineralogy and geology as also botany at the feet of eminent professors and was initiated into chemistry by Rouelle, whose fame as an exponent of the science had attracted pupils from far and near. Besides Lavoisier, Rouelle could boast of such illustrious pupils as Bucquet, Bayen, Macquer and Darcet—each and all of whom made their mark as eminent chemists towards the close of the eighteenth century.

There was thus a decided initial advantage on the side of Lavoisier, whose intellectual equipment enabled him to see things in their true perspective. Priestley often improvised his experiments in a crude manner and performed them clumsily and had sometimes to call in the aid of practised hands like Warltire's to be quite sure of the results and to consult professional chemists or apothecaries like Cadet as regards the purity of the red precipitate he used. He was, thus, often led to draw wrong conclusions. We shall select some typical instances to

illustrate the difference in the mental outlook of each of these great precursors of our science.

Lavoisier started his career as a chemist when he was barely twenty-seven, and his first classical experiment (1772) imparted a rude shock to the then current notions about the constitution of matter. From the time of the old Greek and Hindu philosophers it was held that matter was composed of the four (according to the Hindu, five including "byom" or ether) elements and that these were convertible into one another. Chemists had often noticed that when distilled water was evaporated off even in a clean glass vessel there was invariably a solid residue left. This result was vaguely interpreted as the transmutation of water into earth. Lavoisier caused water to be boiled in a specially devised glass vessel for three months, day and night. He weighed the glass vessel very carefully both before and after the experiment as also the evaporated (distilled) water and the residue, and proved conclusively that the weight of the latter was exactly equal to the diminution in weight of the glass vessel—in other words, that the water invariably dissolves a portion of the glass as is now known to every chemist. It should be noticed that *Lavoisier used the balance as his guide in this as in all his subsequent experiments*. He next took up the question of combustibility of diamond. Darcet, Rouelle, Macquer, Boyle, as also the physicists under the patronage of the Grand Duke of Tuscany had already demonstrated that this precious stone when strongly heated on a porcelain dish slowly disappeared.¹ Lavoisier

¹ There was, however, considerable difference of opinion as regards the cause of this phenomenon, the generally accepted view being that the diamond like phosphorus volatilised away (*vide Hist. Hindu Chem.*, Vol. 1, 2nd Ed., p. 101). It was in 1775, *i.e.*, after the discovery of oxygen, that Lavoisier proved that "fixed air is a compound of carbon with the elastic fluid contained in the calx (of mercury)." He then established the identity of diamond with a variety of carbon as the former also, when burnt in oxygen, yielded the fixed air (carbon dioxide).

in collaboration with Macquer and Cadet proved that diamond when prevented from coming into contact with air remained intact and legitimately concluded that it was a case of ordinary combustion like that of charcoal. But the ground was not yet ready for the full and satisfactory explanation, as oxygen had yet to be discovered. This and the succeeding two years were equally eventful. He burnt phosphorus in a closed vessel and found that one-fifth of the volume of air disappeared and the residual air was unfit for respiration; and knowing the specific gravity of the air he could conclude that this diminution was proportional to the increase in weight of the body burnt. He also proved that sulphur too when burnt, far from losing, gained in weight.

Lavoisier sums up his experiences of 1772 in these memorable words: "Not only sulphur and phosphorus but all bodies, which gain in weight during combustion and calcination, are to be brought under the same category; I am, indeed, inclined to believe that the augmentation in weight of metallic calxes is due to the same cause."¹ Lavoisier now took up in right earnest

¹ Je crus devoir, dit-il, prendre quelques précautions pour m'assurer la propriété de ma découverte. Il y avait à cette époque une correspondance habituelle entre les savants de France et ceux d'Angleterre; il régnait, entre les deux nations, une sorte de rivalité qui donnait de l'importance aux expériences nouvelles, et qui portait quelquefois les écrivains de l'une et l'autre nation à les contester à leur véritable auteur. Je crus donc devoir déposer, le 1^{er} novembre 1772, l'écrit suivant, cacheté, entre les mains du secrétaire de l'Académie. Il était conçu en ces termes: "Il y a environ huit jours que j'ai découvert que le soufre, en brûlant, loin de perdre de son poids, en acquérait au contraire; c'est-à-dire que d'une livre de soufre on pouvait retirer beaucoup plus d'une livre d'acide sulfurique, abstraction faite de l'humidité de l'air; il en est de même du phosphore; cette augmentation de poids vient d'une quantité prodigieuse d'air qui se fixe pendant la combustion et qui se combine avec les vapeurs.

"Cette découverte, que j'ai constatée par des expériences que je regarde comme décisives, m'a fait penser que ce qui s'observait dans le soufre et du phosphore pouvait bien avoir lieu à l'égard de tous les corps qui acquièrent du poids, et par la combustion et la calcination, et je me suis persuadé que l'augmentation de poids des chaux métalliques tentait à la même cause."—Grinaux' *Lavoisier*.

the problem of the increase in weight of lead and tin during calcination. Nearly a century and a half before his time his own countryman, Jean Rey, in 1630, had come to the conclusion that this "increase in weight was due to the fixation of air, which had become thickened and heavy by the vehemence and long continued heat of the fire."¹ Robert Boyle, however, was of opinion—an opinion based upon the old notion of the material nature of fire—that the increase in weight was due to the absorption of the fire particles, which penetrated through the pores of the glass vessel in which the metal was heated. We might profitably recall here the observations of Hooke in this connection.

Hooke distinctly states that "in the dissolution of *sulphureous* (combustible) bodies, by a substance inherent in, and mixed with, the air, which is like, if not the *very same*, with that fixed in saltpetre, a certain part of the bodies is united and mixed, or *dissolved and turned into*, the air, and made to fly up and down with it, in the same manner, as a metalline or other body dissolved into any *menstruum*, doth follow the motions and progress of the *menstruum* till it be precipitated."²

¹ It is of interest to note that Macquer and his collaborator Tillet in 1763 also noticed the increase in weight on calcination. Thus while discussing the increase in the weight of lead on its conversion into litharge, Tillet observes: "It is a true chemical paradox which experience places beyond all doubt; but if it is easy to state the fact, it is not equally easy to assign a satisfactory reason. It is contrary to all physical ideas."—Hoefler, *Hist. Chim.*, II, pp. 386-387.

² Hooke further relates: "That whereas *Salt-peter* is a *menstruum*, when melted and red-hot, that abounds more with those Dissolvent particles, and therefore as a small quantity of it will dissolve a great sulphureous body, so will the dissolution be very quick and violent.

Therefore in the *Eleventh* place, it is observable, that, as in other solutions, if a copious and quick supply of fresh *menstruum*, though but weak, be poured on, or applied to the dissoluble body, it quickly consumes it: So this *menstruum* of the Air, if by Bellows, or any other such contrivance, it be copiously apply'd to the shining body, is found to dissolve it as soon, and as violently as the more strong *menstruum* of melted *Nitre*"—*Alcemic Club Reprints, Hooke*, p. 46.

It should be borne in mind in connexion with this, that the Cabbalist and Rosicrucian Fludd, some fifty years before Hooke, held that "the substance of saltpetre is nothing else but *air* congealed by cold, and he relates that he filled an egg with it, mixed with sulphur and quicklime, and closing the aperture with wax placed the egg under water, where it exploded." Mayow, who was a contemporary of Boyle, had almost hit upon the true explanation; only he failed to isolate the particular constituent of the air which took part in combustion. He, in 1668, at the early age of twenty-three, improved upon Hooke and extended his theory to respiration, and affirmed that there is *something in the air* absolutely necessary to life, which is *conveyed into the blood*. Mayow's views, however, received only scant recognition, for the fame of his great contemporaries, Newton and Boyle, "overshadowed the labours of the less well-known investigators." The editors of the "Medico-physical Works of John Mayow" (Alembic Club Reprints) thus remark: "Mayow's works were not much noticed in his own time, and speedily fell into almost total oblivion. After the great revolution in chemical theory which followed the discovery of oxygen, Mayow's book was discovered in old libraries, where it had remained disregarded for a hundred years; and those who discovered it were astonished to see that the new chemistry, which was rapidly conquering the scientific world, was to be found in this old book."

"Curiously enough, while Boyle seems to have read Mayow's work, he does not appear to have been favourably impressed by his conclusions. Boyle, at the age of fifty-two, had, doubtless, formed his own opinions and was unwilling that they should be disturbed by the speculations, well-founded though they were, of so young a man"—(Ramsay).

The opinion of Boyle, however, prevailed at the time, nay, it was given currency to by the French chemist Lémery whose celebrated treatise, *Course of Chemistry*, was the recognised standard work all along. Lavoisier overthrew this erroneous notion by a simple experiment. He introduced a piece of tin in a closed vessel and weighed it carefully ; it was then placed over a fire and strongly heated. On re-weighing the vessel it was proved that there was only a superficial coating due to the formation of the calx but no loss or gain in weight. He also collected the residual air and found that it had diminished in bulk and was rendered unfit for respiration. Lavoisier thus conclusively proved that the increase in weight of the metal was due to the fixation of a portion of the atmospheric air.

Matters stood thus up till the year 1774. Lavoisier was satisfied that the gain of the metal in weight was due to a portion of the air being fixed but as yet he had no clear conception as to the nature of its particular constituent, which took part in the formation of the calx ; he racked his brains for its isolation but unfortunately the method he adopted proved treacherous.

From time immemorial charcoal had been used in all metallurgical operations for the extraction of the metal from the ores. We all know that it is only a reduction of the oxide of the metal by carbon. The supporters of the phlogistic theory held that as charcoal revived the metal, it simply restored the phlogiston to the calx. In fact charcoal and all carbonaceous matter in general and later on inflammable air (hydrogen) were supposed to be very rich in this imaginary principle. Lavoisier heated a weighed quantity of the calx of lead (minium) and charcoal in a measured volume of air. He obtained the reduced metal and at the same time a volume of a gas which, later on, was identified as carbonic

acid gas; it is this gas which Lavoisier at this stage in his career mistook for oxygen, *i.e.*, the elastic fluid which is fixed in the metal during calcination. It is easy to account for the error into which this great master-mind was led. The reaction, of course, is as follows :

Every tyro in chemistry now knows that carbon dioxide contains its own volume of oxygen but Lavoisier, like his contemporaries, had to grope in the dark. The solution of the vexed problem was now at hand. Fortunately, there exists a metal which, when heated in contact with air, is converted into its calx, and the latter again, when more strongly heated, is reduced to the former metallic state. This peculiar property is shared by the red precipitate or mercurius precipitatus per se. Eck de Sulzbach had already noticed this remarkable phenomenon in 1480 but he failed to draw any conclusion therefrom. Bayen, a fellow-student of Lavoisier, heated a weighed quantity of mercury calx in a retort of known capacity communicating with a receiver of known volume inverted over water. The volume of gas evolved could thus be measured. This he did and he also weighed the metallic mercury formed. He was startled with the result; here was a calx which, heated by itself without the addition of charcoal to provide the phlogiston necessary for reduction, not only yielded the metal but also a gas. Unfortunately, he did not examine the nature of the gas liberated nor did he even distinguish it from the fixed air obtained on reducing the calx with charcoal, though he noted that the volume of the gas evolved was in both cases approximately the same.¹ Bayen was thus on the eve of a great discovery,

¹ $2\text{HgO} = 2\text{Hg} + \text{O}_2$; $2\text{HgO} + \text{C} = 2\text{Hg} + \text{CO}_2$.

There would be as many molecules of oxygen liberated as those of carbon dioxide hence the volumes would be the same.

namely, of oxygen, but he missed it by a hair's breadth. This experiment was conducted in April, 1774. On the 1st of August of the same year Priestley also repeated the same experiment, which we shall allow him to describe in his own words : " With this apparatus, after a variety of other experiments, on the 1st of August, 1774, I endeavoured to extract air from *mercurius calcinatus per se*, and I presently found that, by means of this lens, air was expelled from it very readily. Having got about three or four times as much as the bulk of my materials, I admitted water to it, and found that it was not imbibed by it. But what surprised me more than I can well express was, that a candle burned in this air with a remarkably vigorous flame. I was utterly at a loss how to account for it.....but, however, being at Paris in the October following.....I frequently mentioned my surprise at the kind of air which I had got from this preparation to Mr. Lavoisier, Mr. Le Roy, and several other philosophers who honoured me with their notice in that city, and who, I dare say, cannot fail to recollect the circumstance. *At the same time I had no suspicion that the air which I had got from the mercurius calcinatus was even wholesome, so far was I from knowing what it was that I had really found. In this ignorance of the real nature of this kind of air, I continued from this time (November) to the 1st of March following.* * ** Till the 1st of March, 1775, I had so little suspicion of its being whole-some, that I had not even thought of applying to it the test of nitrous air; but it occurred to me at last to make the experiment and putting one measure of nitrous air to two measures of this air, I found not only that it was diminished, but that it was diminished quite as much as common air, and that the redness of the mixture was likewise equal to that of a similar mixture of nitrous and common air. After this I had no doubt

but that the air from *merc. calcinatus* was *fit for respiration*, and that it had all the other genuine properties of common air. But I did not take notice of what I might have observed if I had not been so fully possessed by the notion of there being no air better than common air, that the redness was really deeper, and diminution some thing greater, than common air would have admitted. *I now concluded that all the constituent parts of the air were equally and in their proper proportion imbibed in the preparation of this substance, and also in the process of making red lead.*" It will thus be seen that in this respect Priestley held exactly the same views as Rey in 1630.

The next step, as Harcourt points out, in Priestley's inquiry was the employment of Mayow's mice, which convinced him that this air was *longer* respirable than common air; but his ideas of it were less accurate than Mayow's, for instead of considering it, with him, *a constituent part of nitric acid*, he thought it *a compound of nitric acid and earth*; and in December, 1777, "no doubt remained on his mind that atmospheric air, or the thing that we breathe, consists of the nitrous [nitric] acid and earth, with so much phlogiston as is necessary to its elasticity, and likewise so much more as is necessary to bring it from its state of perfect purity to the mean condition in which we find it" (*Phil. Mag.*, 1846).

We have already seen that Lavoisier was on the lookout for the particular constituent which was responsible for the formation of the calx, but was as yet unsuccessful in separating it from the air and thus proving its individual distinctive property. It was at this very psychological moment that Priestley, who happened to be accidentally at Paris as a companion of Lord Shelburne in his continental tour, in the course of his conversations

with Lavoisier incidentally narrated his own experiences with regard to heating the red calx of mercury. The idea at once flashed across Lavoisier's mind that probably the long looked-for gas was at last in sight. He repeated the experiment and it led to most momentous and epoch-making results—the real explanation of the process of combustion. Lavoisier, in fact, not only isolated oxygen (vital air) but recognised it as a distinct constituent of atmospheric air and systematically explained the part it plays in combustion and respiration, and thus at one bound left Priestley far behind, as will be evident from the latter's recorded opinion in 1775 quoted above.¹ Henceforward, as Hartog tersely puts it, "Lavoisier acted as a sieve to separate the inaccurate work and conclusions of Priestley from the accurate" (Art. on Priestley, *Dict. Nat. Biog.*).

I have devoted some considerable space to the discussion of the question, "Who discovered oxygen?" because the answer cannot be given in one word. It all hinges upon what is really meant by the term discovery. An eminent English chemist writing eighty years ago thus sums up his views: "Whoever may be called the discoverer of oxygen, whether Hooke and Mayow, who first inferred its existence in nitre and in air—or Boyle,

¹ That Priestley did not, like Lavoisier, keep records of his experiments as is done by ordinary laboratory students and when writing his papers had to draw upon memory—often a deceptive agent—is borne out by his own words: "I cannot, at this distance of time, recollect what it was that I had in view in making this experiment (of extracting 'air' from *mercurius calcinatus*)"—*On Dephlogisticated Air* (Alembic Club Reprints, No. 7, p. 15). As a proof of Lavoisier's unstinted admiration for the English chemists' discoveries of different kinds of "air" may be cited the following. Speaking specially of Priestley he says: "Ce travail, dit Lavoisier en parlant des premiers travaux de Priestley, peut être regardé comme le plus pénible et le plus intéressant qui ait paru depuis M. Hales sur la fixation et le dégagement de l'air. Aucun des ouvrages modernes ne m'a paru plus propre à faire sentir combien la physique et la chimie offrent encore de nouvelles routes à parcourir"—Grimaux, *Lavoisier*.

who first disengaged the elastic gas from minium, or Hales, who collected it from the same material, or Nieuwentyt, who attributed its elasticity to the expansion of the fire particles lodged in the minium, supposing fire to be a particular fluid which maintains its own essence and figure, remaining always fire, though not always burning,—or Priestley who observed that it supported combustion—or Lavoisier who distinguished it as a gas *sui generis*, and determined its principal combinations,—if the question be, which of these names deserves the highest place in the history of this discovery, a philosopher I apprehend might be apt to hesitate—especially perhaps between those which stand *first* in the list, and that which stands *last*”—(Harcourt).

But it was a long time before Lavoisier's views, highly lucid and illuminating though they were, met with universal acceptance. In fact, he had to work alone, single-handed and up-hill for twelve tedious years even after the discovery of oxygen (1774-1786) before his victory was complete. It is remarkable that the "geometers," not being under the tyranny of preconceived notions, were the first to accept Lavoisier's views, whereas the chemists even while admitting the force of his incontestable proofs long hesitated to declare their adhesion to the new doctrine. Berthollet was the first to rally round his banner in 1785 and he was soon followed by Fourcroy and Guyton de Morveau in 1786.

Among the English adversaries there was an eminent chemist, whose authority was held in respect, namely,

¹ It is generally held that it was the non-French chemists who alone opposed Lavoisier. But this is far from being the case. In a French treatise on chemistry written by Démește in 1779 the very name of Lavoisier occurs scarcely once. Although chemistry soon came to be designated as the "French science," during the life-time of Lavoisier, at any rate, up till the year 1792, it was not so. In fact, Lavoisier himself protested against this designation. The new chemistry he naturally claimed as his own—"c'est la mienne," as he said.

Kirwan, who attacked Lavoisier's doctrines in his *Essay on Phlogiston*. Madame Lavoisier translated the work into French, and Guyton de Morveau, Lavoisier, Laplace, Monge, Berthollet and Fourcroy subjected this work to a severe criticism chapter by chapter. Kirwan resisted for a time but he was at length so much convinced of the truth of the new doctrine against which he had combated so long that in 1792 he wrote to Berthollet: "I lay down my arms, I abandon the phlogistic doctrine."

While the scientific world was slowly coming round to Lavoisier's views, Priestley could never shake himself free from the trammels of his preconceived notions and always explained the phenomenon of combustion according to his phlogistic theory. Thus a candle when it burnt in air simply disengaged its phlogiston to the air, which (*i. e.*, nitrogen *plus* the carbon dioxide), accordingly, was named "phlogisticated air," whereas the same candle or a piece of charcoal burnt longer and more vividly in the "new species of air" (extracted from red calx)—being capable of taking more phlogiston from them it was called "dephlogisticated air." One of his earliest experiments was suggested by the memoir of Cavendish on "Inflammable Air." Cavendish was led to suppose that inflammable air was phlogiston in the free state. In order to test this supposition Priestley placed some minium in a crucible within a tall cylinder filled with inflammable air and inverted over water. He then began to heat the minium by means of a burning lens. "As soon as the minium was dry, by means of the heat thrown upon it I observed that it became black, and then ran in the form of perfect lead; at the same time that the air diminished at a great rate, the water ascending within the receiver." He concludes "that phlogiston is the same thing as inflammable air, and is contained in a combining state in metals, just as fixed

air is contained in chalk and other calcareous substances both being equally capable of being expelled again in the form of air." He could not, of course, detect the formation of water in the process, as he was carrying on his experiment in a jar over water and thus he missed the glory of being the discoverer of the composition of water. Priestley also believed that inflammable air came from iron or zinc when these metals were treated with dilute sulphuric acid, and found an additional experimental support for the view that metals contain phlogiston. To quote Thorpe: "The discovery of oxygen was the death-blow to phlogiston. Here was the thing which had been groped for for years, and which many had even stumbled over in the searching, but had never grasped. Priestley indeed grasped it, but he failed to see the magnitude and true importance of what he had found. It was far otherwise with Lavoisier. He at once recognised in Priestley's new air the one fact needed to complete the overthrow of Stahl's doctrine; and now every stronghold of phlogistonism was in turn made to yield. Priestley, however, never surrendered, even when nearly every phlogistian but he had given up the fight or gone over to the enemy. When age compelled him to leave his laboratory he continued to serve the old cause in his study, and almost his last publication was the *Doctrine of Phlogiston Established*."

The third of the illustrious triumvirate, whose name is indissolubly associated with the discovery of oxygen, is Carl Wilhelm Scheele. As an experimenter and discoverer he is simply unrivalled. It has been justly said that he made more discoveries in the course of a dozen years or so than all his contemporary chemists taken together. The claims of Scheele to the independent discovery of oxygen have never been disputed, and it has now been placed beyond doubt that Scheele

had obtained the gas as early as Priestley's first isolation of it, although his printed account of the discovery appeared about two years after Priestley's. Scheele obtained his "fire-air" by several methods. He heated precipitate of mercury *per se*. He also obtained the gas by heating calxes of silver and gold, as also by treating pyrolusite with oil of vitriol and also by heating nitre. His method of collecting the gas was also peculiar. He used empty bladders for this purpose. Let us give one or two excerpts from his experiments. "I filled a bottle, which contained 10 ounces of water, with this gas. I then placed a small lighted candle in it; scarcely had this been done when the candle began to burn with a large flame, whereby it gave out such a bright light that it was sufficient to dazzle the eyes. I mixed one part of this air with three parts of that kind of air in which fire would not burn; I had here an air which was like the ordinary air in every respect. Since this air is necessarily required for the origination of fire, and makes up about the third part of our common air, I shall call it after this, for the sake of shortness, "fire-air"; but the other air which is not in the least serviceable for the fiery phenomena and makes up about two-thirds of our air, I shall designate after this with the name already known, of Vitiated air." Scheele used as absorbents of the fire air (*i*) oil of turpentine, (*ii*) freshly precipitated ferrous hydroxide, (*iii*) moist iron filings, (*iv*) liver of sulphur, and (*v*) phosphorus. With the aid of these he separated the "other kind of air in which fire would not burn." Scheele had thus no difficulty in proving that- "*air must be composed of elastic fluids of two kinds.*" It will be seen that Scheele's views were almost the same as those we hold to-day. But as he was a follower of Stahl, his explanation of the burning of the candle was the same as Priestley's, namely, the

transference of phlogiston to the air, and he was thus led into absurd blunders. The absorption of fire-air by liver of sulphur he explained on the assumption that heat is a compound of fire-air with Stahl's phlogiston and "that by the action of a double affinity the fire-air in his experiment had combined with the *phlogiston* of the liver of sulphur, and that the compound had passed through the pores of the glass by which it had before been confined."

In the history of scientific discoveries it is often found that chance plays a great part but it should not be taken in the gambler's sense. As the great Pasteur once said: "In the field of observation chance only favours the mind which is prepared;" in other words, the mind must be predisposed towards the reception of new truths, hence the property of the new gas which under "Priestley's observation led to nothing, in the hands of Lavoisier gave rise to one of the most important investigations in the annals of Chemistry"—(Harcourt). Priestley's frame of mind was just the reverse and antithesis of that of Lavoisier as he often based his conclusions on random haphazard experiments To quote his own words: "That more is owing to what we call chance, that is philosophically speaking, to the observation of events arising from unknown causes, than to any proper design or pre-conceived theory in this business." Eck de Sulzbach is probably the first chemist who in 1489 demonstrated experimentally that the metals increase in weight when calcined; what we now call metallic oxides are named by him fixed ashes of the metal, which is exactly the term used in the Hindu chemical treatises (घातुभस्म). The mercurius calcinatus *per se* was prepared by him and called fixed mercury; he distinctly says that when the latter is subjected to distillation it disengages a spirit (invisible gas). He, thus, like Bayen narrowly missed being the discoverer of oxygen.

It has been well said that no single discovery or invention has been made all at once by a single man unless it be that of logarithms; in fact, there is nothing new under the sun. Every discovery has its origin in the earlier observation of some previous philosopher, but the appellation of the discoverer should best be applied to the man who makes a discovery and elucidates natural phenomena in its light. It now remains for us to conclude with the considered opinions of some more English chemists who have bestowed much thought and study upon the subject. Says Rodwell: "Who is the discoverer? Is it the man who obtains a new body for the first time without recognising that it is different from anything else, or is it the man who demonstrates its true nature and properties.....? If the latter, assuredly Lavoisier discovered oxygen... Priestley's observations read like the writings of the seventeenth century, Lavoisier's like those of the nineteenth.Not without reason, said M. Wurtz, "La Chimie est une science française. Elle fut instituée par Lavoisier d'immortelle mémoire."¹ The petty jealousies which disfigured the history of science during the end of the last and commencement of the present century (19th) ought to find no place in our minds. The republic of Science is large enough for every man to receive his due." Mr. Pattison Muir reviewing this question observes: "To co-ordinate the facts of science, to describe these facts accurately, to express them in a language which should make it easy to put together facts that were similar and to keep apart those which were unlike, and at the same time to overthrow the phlogistic theory; these were the tasks waiting to be accomplished at the beginning of the last quarter of the eighteenth century. It is not

¹ Chemistry is a French science. It was founded by Lavoisier of immortal memory.

often that the power of destroying and the power of reconstructing are united in so extraordinary a degree as they were united in Lavoisier, the greatest of all Chemists."

It will thus be seen that although some English chemists cannot forgive Lavoisier for what is according to them the appropriation of the credit which rightly belongs to Priestley, there are others, on the contrary, in whom the innate sense of justice and fairplay so characteristic of the great nation finds full expression.¹

It will be instructive here to draw a parallel from the history of the discovery of the composition of water. Cavendish's experiments of 1781 were communicated to Priestley, who had them reproduced with the help of Wartire. But as Priestley was obsessed with the notion that charcoal was very rich in phlogiston, he prepared the latter by heating moist charcoal in a gun-barrel. It will thus be seen that Priestley's so-called phlogiston was a mixture of carbonic oxide and hydrogen—in fact, it was what is now known as water-gas. This is the initial blunder which Priestley and his friend James Watt committed; both these philosophers laboured under the misconception that inflammable air was the same from whatever source it might be obtained. "Priestley's inflammable gas, which he used, cannot have contained

¹ Thomson in his *History of Chemistry* takes Lavoisier severely to task for his omission of any mention of Priestley's name in connection with the discovery of oxygen, in the paper communicated to the Academy in 1775. He says: "I confess that this seems to me capable of no other explanation than a wish to claim for himself the discovery of oxygen gas, though he knew well that that discovery had been previously made by another." But Thomson seems to contradict himself and almost to give away his case when he says in another place: "It is not the man who forms the first vague notion of a thing that really adds to the stock of our knowledge, but he who demonstrates its truth and accurately determines its nature." Again, "It is obvious, however, that Lavoisier was on the way to make these discoveries, and had neither Scheele nor Priestley been fortunate enough to hit upon oxygen gas, it is exceedingly likely that he would himself have been able to make that discovery."

more than one-fifteenth of its weight of hydrogen and if it had proved anything it would have proved that water consists chiefly of carbon"—(Harcourt). Moreover, Priestley and Watt also accepted the prevailing doctrine of the convertibility of air into water and *vice versa*, and it was on this basis that they explained the formation of water by explosion.

"Cavendish begins his memoir entitled *Experiments on Air* with an account of a repetition of an experiment of Warltire's related by Priestley, in which a mixture of inflammable air and ordinary air was exploded in a copper vessel, with the result that he observed a loss of a few grains in weight; it is also stated by Warltire that if the explosion took place in a glass vessel it became dewy, which confirmed an opinion, he had long entertained, that common air deposits its moisture by phlogistication"—(Ramsay).

"Cavendish was on the look-out for an explanation as to what had become of "*the air lost*" in the combustion of inflammable air with common air, and he undertook several preliminary trials, by which he searched for the lost gases. He tried (1) whether they were *changed* into carbonic acid; (2) whether they were "*changed*" into nitric acid; (3) whether they were "*changed*" into sulphuric acid; he *negatived* by conclusive experiments these three suppositions of *condensation*; at this crisis of his inquiry Warltire burnt inflammable gas and common air in a vessel which he imagined to be close, and finding a very sensible loss of weight, concluded, with Scheele that ponderable matter had passed through the vessel's pore in the form of heat; at the same time he repeated an observation, made also by others, that in the combustion *water* was deposited from the air, in which he supposed it *to have been contained*: to the mind of Cavendish, deeply meditating what might be the form of

matter into which the *lost airs* could have been *condensed*, this inaccurate experiment immediately suggested the light for which he was watching"—(Harcourt).

There is thus a strong family likeness between the mind of Lavoisier perplexed over the solution of the difficulty regarding the particular constituent of air responsible for combustion and that of Cavendish anxiously intent upon the problem of the disappearance of two volumes of inflammable air and one volume of dephlogisticated air which practically vanished on explosion. Hence, if Priestley were to be credited with the discovery of oxygen, Warltire had still stronger claims to be regarded as the discoverer of the composition of water.

And as regards Watt, Ramsay thus interprets his conception on the matter: "This letter ¹ of Watt's [to Black] shows clearly the difference of the two points of view of the new and the old school. While Lavoisier and his followers advanced the view which is now universally accepted, namely, that hydrogen and oxygen, when exploded together, combine to form water and nothing else, Watt was inclined to believe that the water was present in a concealed state in all gases, hydrogen and oxygen among others; and that it was thrown out by the act of combination, and was not the product of the combination."² It should be noted here that Watt tenaciously clings to this view even in 1788, although Lavoisier by his crucial

¹ "I have nothing else new in the philosophical way, except repetitions by Dr. P. of his experiments on the deflagration of D^d [dephlogisticated] and inf^l [inflammable] airs, in [which nitrous acid is always produced. As the deflagrations were performed in copper vessels, the acid is saturated with copper and is green, but becomes blue on the addition of a small quantity of common spirit of nitre. It appears, however, that more than 9/10ths of the liquor thus produced is water, which probably in its own form constitutes the greater part of the mass of air. I think it highly probable that the acid proceeds from the inflammable air, and that the D^d [dephlogisticated] air acts the same part that it does in the burning of sulphur and phosphorus."

² Ramsay,— *The Life and Letters of Joseph Black*, p. 90.

experiment in 1783 had satisfactorily established the composition of water.

Here, again, it is necessary to revert for a moment to another much-debated controversy, namely, the priority of the discovery of the composition of water. Cavendish, of course, proved in 1781 by his classical experiments that two volumes of inflammable air and one volume of dephlogisticated air, when exploded by electric sparks, disappeared almost entirely. This is now practically conceded by all parties. As Ramsay says: "These experiments were due to Cavendish; all that Lavoisier did was to show the true nature of the phenomena." But here the question naturally arises—who is the greater of the two—the discoverer of facts or the man who interprets and systematises them? The very experiments of Cavendish when repeated by Lavoisier in conjunction with Laplace enabled the great French chemist to deal a final blow to the phlogistians. The prevailing belief was that the metals were composed of calx and phlogiston and that on their dissolution in acids the latter was set free and it was even confounded with inflammable air. But Lavoisier now came forward with the true explanation. The metal decomposed the water uniting with its oxygen to form a calx liberating hydrogen; the calx in turn, dissolved in the acid forming a salt. Nay, Lavoisier fortified himself in his position by performing the reverse experiment in collaboration with Meunier. He passed steam over red-hot iron with the result that hydrogen was copiously liberated with the formation of the magnetic iron oxide, *ethiops martial*. Ramsay pathetically exclaims: "It is curious to follow the reasoning which made such an exceptionally acute thinker as Cavendish deliberately reject the true explanation." Ramsay in order to establish or rather vindicate Cavendish's claims naïvely says: "All that Lavoisier did was to

show the true nature of the phenomenon." Yes, herein lies the greatness of the French chemist. Mellor also evidently inclines to the same view (*vide J. W. Mellor, A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry*, Vol. I, p. 143).

The controversy, which raged with some degree of bitterness during the life-time of Newton and even after his death over the question of the priority of the invention of fluxions or infinitesimals, may also be mentioned here. Leibnitz, backed by eminent continental mathematicians, claimed it as his own. On the other hand, Newton, or rather his friends maintained with equal pertinacity that the German philosopher, while on a visit to England in 1673, had his hint from Collins to whom Newton had communicated the principles of the method.

While discussing the controversial subject of the discovery of oxygen I have been at the pains to quote the opinions of some eminent English chemists, who, though they have not grudged to vote the major and minor premises, yet, with the exception of one or two, have shrunk from drawing the logical conclusion.

It is not necessary to belittle the one in order to magnify the other. Each was great in his own way and has extended the boundaries of our science.
